

Household Level Questionnaire FINAL VERSION

Date of the surveyyyyy-mm-dd

Country Benin Tanzania**Province****District****Ward**

Village**Village chair man**

ENUMERATOR*Select your name***Household ID**

Name of Household Head

Questionnaire started on DATE*The date you started the questionnaire*yyyy-mm-dd

Questionnaire started on TIME*Indicate the hour you started the questionnaire*hh:mm

HOUSEHOLD SOCIOECONOMIC AND DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

Name of the respondent

Phone Number of the respondent

What is the respondent's relationship to the head of the household?

- Head
- Spouse
- Child
- Grandchild
- Parent/Parent-in-law
- Son/Daughter-in-law
- Adopted/Foster/Stepchild
- Other relative
- Non-relative

Now we want to record all members of your household

A household consists of all people who live under the same roof, eat from the same pot and share expenditures. A person is considered as a member if he/she lived for 6 months or longer in this household within the past 12 months

Size of the household

1

*** No**

*** Name and Given name**

*** Age**

*** Sex**

- Male
- Female

*** Level of education**

- None/Kindergarten
- Primary
- Secondaary
- University

*** Last class completed with succes in the primary school**

- CI
- CP
- CE1
- CE2
- CM1
- CM2

*** Last class completed with succes in the secondary school**

- 6e
- 5e
- 4e
- 3e
- 2nd
- 1ère
- Tle
- Autre

*** Last class completed with succes at University**

- 1ère année
- 2ème année
- 3ème année
- 4ème année
- 5ème année
- 6ème année
- 7ème année
- 8ème année
- Autre

* Specify Other class completed

Total members in the Household

Type of road to access the village

- Tarred road
- Trail suitable for vehicle
- Trail unsuitable for vehicles
- Other

Other type of road to access in the village

Type of road to access the village

Distance from the household to the center of the village in Km?

Distance from the household to the nearest market in Km?

LAND USE AND OWNERSHIP

» Total land cultivated during the agricultural campaign 2017-2018 (in ha)

In case of intercropping, please report the size of the entire plot for the main crop of the intercropped plot

Organic cotton

Did any member of household cultivate Organic cotton

- No
- Yes

Total area of Organic cotton (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated organic cotton

Conventional cotton

Did any member of household cultivate Conventional cotton

- No
 Yes

Total area of Conventional cotton (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated conventional cotton

Maize

Did any member of household cultivate Maize

- No
 Yes

Total area of Maize (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated maize

Rice

Did any member of household cultivate Rice

- No
 Yes

Total area of Rice (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated rice

Millet

Did any member of household cultivate Millet

- No
 Yes

Total area of Millet (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated millet

Sorghum

Did any member of household cultivate Sorghum

- No
 Yes

Total area of Sorghum (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated organic sorghum

Sesame

Did any member of household cultivate Sesame

- No
 Yes

Total area of Sesame (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated sesame

Vegetables (specify)

Did any member of household cultivate Vegetables

- No
 Yes

List of the vegetables cultivated

Total area of Vegetables (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated Vegetables

Sunflower

Did any member of household cultivate Sunflower

- No
 Yes

Total area of Sunflower (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated Sunflower

Greengram

Did any member of household cultivate Greengram

- No
 Yes

Total area of Greengram (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated Greengram

Yam

Did any member of household cultivate Yam

No

Yes

Total area of Yam (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated Yam

Soybean

Did any member of household cultivate Soybean

No

Yes

Total area of Soybean (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated Soybean

Cassava

Did any member of household cultivate Cassava

No

Yes

Total area of Cassava (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated Cassava

Cashewnut

Did any member of household cultivate Cashewnut

No

Yes

Total area of Cashewnut (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated Cashewnut

Pea of earth (voandzou)

Did any member of household cultivate Pea of earth (voandzou)

- No
 Yes

Total area of Pea of earth (voandzou) (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated Pea of earth (voandzou)

Sweet potato

Did any member of household cultivate Sweet potato

- No
 Yes

Total area of Sweet potato (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated Sweet potato

Groundnut

Did any member of household cultivate Groundnut

- No
 Yes

Total area of Groundnut (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated Groundnut

Bean

Did any member of household cultivate Bean

- No
 Yes

Total area of Bean (Niébé/Haricot) (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated Bean

Other 1

First other crop cultivated by the household

- No
 Yes

Speicify Other crops 1

Please written the name of other crop cultivated by the household

Total area of Other crop 1 (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated this crop

Other 2

Second other crop cultivated by the household

No

Yes

Speicify Other crops 2

Please written the name of other crop cultivated by the household

Total area of Other crop 2 (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated this crop

Other 3

Third other crop cultivated by the household

No

Yes

Speicify Other crops 3

Please written the name of other crop cultivated by the household

Total area of Other crop 3 (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated this crop

Other 4

Fourth other crop cultivated by the household

No

Yes

Speicify Other crops 4

Please written the name of other crop cultivated by the household

Total area of Other crop 4 (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated this crop

Other 5

Fifth other crop cultivated by the household

No

Yes

Speicify Other crops 5

Please written the name of other crop cultivated by the household

Total area of Other crop 5 (in ha)

For all household members together who cultivated this crop

» Fallow land, land rented in and rented out, land ownership

» » Checking the total cultivated land size

+++++

According to their answers the total area cultivated is given by the sum above. Write down this sum

Is the total land area that the household cultivates equal to ha?

if No (revise previous answers); if Yes (go to next question)

No

Yes

Total land area under fallow (in ha)

Total land area rented in (in ha)

Total land owned (in ha)

Total land area rented out (in ha)

» Checking the total cultivated land available

+

According to their answers of the Total land rented in + Total land owned is given by the sum above. write down this sum

++

according to their answers of the total land under fallow+ Total land cultivated + Total land rented is given by the sum above. write down this sum

Is the equals to the ?

Please revise previous questions related to land size if both sums are inequal

No

Yes

INDIVIDUAL COTTON PRODUCERS IN THE HOUSEHOLD

Name of the first "cotton producer"

In which of the following cotton production methods, is he or she involved in?

Only Organic

Only Conventional

Both

Number of conventional cotton plots

Number of Organic cotton plots

Is there another cotton producer in the household

No

Yes

» Second cotton producer in the household

Name of the second "cotton producer"

In which of the following cotton production methods, is he or she involved in?

- Only Organic
- Only Conventional
- Both

Number of conventional cotton plots

Number of Organic cotton plots

Is there another cotton producer in the household

- No
- Yes

» Third cotton producer in the household

Name of the third "cotton producer"

In which of the following cotton production methods, is he or she involved in?

- Only Organic
- Only Conventional
- Both

Number of conventional cotton plots

Number of Organic cotton plots

Is there another cotton producer in the household

- No
- Yes

» Fourth cotton producer in the household

Name of the fourth "cotton producer"

In which of the following cotton production methods, is he or she involved in?

- Only Organic
- Only Conventional
- Both

Number of conventional cotton plots

Number of Organic cotton plots

Is there another cotton producer in the household

- No
- Yes

» Fifth cotton producer in the household

Name of the fifth "cotton producer"

In which of the following cotton production methods, is he or she involved in?

- Only Organic
- Only Conventional
- Both

Number of conventional cotton plots

Number of Organic cotton plots

Is there another cotton producer in the household

- No
- Yes

» Sixth cotton producer in the household

Name of the sixth "cotton producer"

In which of the following cotton production methods, is he or she involved in?

- Only Organic
- Only Conventional
- Both

Number of conventional cotton plots

Number of Organic cotton plots

Is there another cotton producer in the household

- No
- Yes

» Seventh cotton producer in the household

Name of the seventh "cotton producer"

In which of the following cotton production methods, is he or she involved in?

- Only Organic
- Only Conventional
- Both

Number of conventional cotton plots

Number of Organic cotton plots

Is there another cotton producer in the household

- No
- Yes

» Eighth cotton producer in the household

Name of the eighth "cotton producer"

In which of the following cotton production methods, is he or she involved in?

- Only Organic
- Only Conventional
- Both

Number of conventional cotton plots

Number of Organic cotton plots

Is there another cotton producer in the household

- No
- Yes

» Nineth cotton producer in the household

Name of the Nineth "cotton producer"

In which of the following cotton production methods, is he or she involved in?

- Only Organic
- Only Conventional
- Both

Number of conventional cotton plots

Number of Organic cotton plots

Is there another cotton producer in the household

- No
- Yes

» Tenth cotton producer in the household

Name of the tenth "cotton producer"

In which of the following cotton production methods, is he or she involved in?

- Only Organic
- Only Conventional
- Both

Number of conventional cotton plots

Number of Organic cotton plots

» Verification of the number of cultivated cotton plots

+++++

Please write the total sum above here (for conventional cotton)

+++++

Please write the total sum above here (for organic cotton)

Does your household in total cultivate conventional cotton plots

- No
- Yes

Does your household in total cultivate organic cotton plots?

- No
- Yes

SHARE OF COTTON INCOME

What is the share of cotton income on the household total monetary income?

10 stones = all monetary income: how many 'stones' from cotton?

EARNING OPPORTUNITIES APART FROM COTTON CULTIVATION

» BEGINNING OF THE SEASON

What would the Children (Male and Female [7-14] years) of the household who work on your cotton plots earn if they would do other work (e.g. non-cotton farm work, non-farm work, ...) at the beginning of the growing season, for instance instead of doing land preparation or sowing at your own cotton plots?

Daily wage rate in FCFA (amount in franc cfa)

What would the Women (Female $\geq$ 15 Years) of the household who work on your cotton plots earn if they would do other work (e.g. non-cotton farm work, non-farm work, ...) at the beginning of the growing season, for instance instead of doing land preparation or sowing at your own cotton plots?

Daily wage rate in FCFA (amount in franc cfa)

What would the Men (Male $\geq$ 15 years) of the household who work on your cotton plots earn if they would do other work (e.g. non-cotton farm work, non-farm work, ...) at the beginning of the growing season, for instance instead of doing land preparation or sowing at your own cotton plots?

Daily wage rate in FCFA (amount in franc cfa)

» MIDDLE OF THE SEASON

What would the Children (Male and Female [7-14] years) of the household who work on your cotton plots earn if they would do other work (e.g. non-cotton farm work, non-farm work, ...) at the middle of the growing season, for instance instead of weeding, fertilizer application, or pesticides application at your own cotton plots?

Daily wage rate in FCFA (amount in franc cfa)

What would the Women (Female $\geq$ 15 Years) of the household who work on your cotton plots earn if they would do other work (e.g. non-cotton farm work, non-farm work, ...) at the middle of the growing season, for instance instead of weeding, fertilizer application, or pesticides application at your own cotton plots?

Daily wage rate in FCFA (amount in franc cfa)

What would the Men (Male $\geq$ 15 years) of the household who work on your cotton plots earn if they would do other work (e.g. non-cotton farm work, non-farm work, ...) at the middle of the growing season, for instance instead of weeding, fertilizer application, or pesticides application at your own cotton plots?

Daily wage rate in FCFA (amount in franc cfa)

» END OF THE SEASON

What would the Children (Male and Female [7-14] years) of the household who work on your cotton plots earn if they would do other work (e.g. non-cotton farm work, non-farm work, ...) at the end of the growing season, for instance instead of harvesting or sorting cotton at/from your own cotton plots?

Daily wage rate in FCFA (amount in franc cfa)

What would the Women (Female >= 15 Years) of the household who work on your cotton plots earn if they would do other work (e.g. non-cotton farm work, non-farm work, ...) at the end of the growing season, for instance instead of harvesting or sorting cotton at/from your own cotton plots?

Daily wage rate in FCFA (amount in franc cfa)

What would the Men (Male >= 15 years) of the household who work on your cotton plots earn if they would do other work (e.g. non-cotton farm work, non-farm work, ...) at the end of the growing season, for instance instead of harvesting or sorting cotton at/from your own cotton plots?

Daily wage rate in FCFA (amount in franc cfa)

FOOD CONSUMPTION: DIVERSITY OF THE DIET

Cereals (bread, maize, sorghum, porridge, etc), in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Cereals (bread, maize, sorghum, porridge, etc), in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

White tubers and roots (white potatoes, white yam, white cassava, or other foods made from roots), in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

White tubers and roots (white potatoes, white yam, white cassava, or other foods made from roots), in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Vitamin a rich vegetables and tubers (carrot, sweet potato, red sweet pepper), in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Vitamin a rich vegetables and tubers (carrot, sweet potato, red sweet pepper), in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Dark green leafy vegetables, in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Dark green leafy vegetables, in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Other vegetables, in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Other vegetables, in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Vitamin A rich fruits (ripe mango, ripe papaya, dried peach, and 100% fruit juice made from these + other), in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Vitamin A rich fruits (ripe mango, ripe papaya, dried peach, and 100% fruit juice made from these + other), in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Other fruits, in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Other fruits, in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Organ meat (liver, kidney, heart or other organ meats or blood-based foods), in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Organ meat (liver, kidney, heart or other organ meats or blood-based foods), in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Flesh meats, in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Flesh meats, in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Eggs, in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Eggs, in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Fish and seafood, in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Fish and seafood, in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Legumes, nuts and seeds (seed: all other seeds except cereals), in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Legumes, nuts and seeds (seed: all other seeds except cereals), in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Milk and milk products, in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Milk and milk products, in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Oils and fats, in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Oils and fats, in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Sweets , in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Sweets , in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

Spices, condiments, beverages (beverages: coffee, tea, alcoholic beverages), in the past 24 hours

This food item was saved in the household in the past 24 hours

- No
 Yes

Spices, condiments, beverages (beverages: coffee, tea, alcoholic beverages), in the past 7 days

This food item was served in the household in the past 7 days

- No
 Yes

FOOD SECURITY INDICATORS

You were worried your household would run out of food because of a lack of money or other resources in the past 12 months?

- Never
 Rarely
 Sometimes
 Often

Your household were unable to eat healthy and nutritious food because of a lack of money or other resources in the past 12 months?

- Never
 Rarely
 Sometimes
 Often

Your household ate only a few kinds of foods because of a lack of money or other resources in the past 12 months?

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often

Your household had to skip a meal because there was not enough money or other resources to get food in the past 12 months?

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often

Your household ate less than you thought you should because of a lack of money or other resources in the past 12 months?

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often

Your household ran out of food because of a lack of money or other resources in the past 12 months?

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often

Your household were hungry but did not eat because there was not enough money or other resources for food in the past 12 months?

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often

Your household went without eating for a whole day because of a lack of money or other resources in the past 12 months?

- Never
- Rarely
- Sometimes
- Often

PERIODS OF HUNGER

Have your household experienced any hungry period in the past 12 months?

The hungry period is the time during which one member of the household or more goes without three meals a day.

- No
- Yes

How many hungry periods did your household experience in the past 12 months?

When did the first hungry period in the past 12 months begin?

yyyy-mm-dd

When did the first hungry period in the past 12 months end?

yyyy-mm-dd

When did the second hungry period in the past 12 months begin?

yyyy-mm-dd

When did the second hungry period in the past 12 months end?

yyyy-mm-dd

When did the third hungry period in the past 12 months begin?

yyyy-mm-dd

When did the third hungry period in the past 12 months end?

yyyy-mm-dd

When did the fourth hungry period in the past 12 months begin?

yyyy-mm-dd

When did the fourth hungry period in the past 12 months end?

yyyy-mm-dd

When did the fifth hungry period in the past 12 months begin?

yyyy-mm-dd

When did the fifth hungry period in the past 12 months end?

yyyy-mm-dd

ELECTRICITY AND COMMUNICATION SERVICES

Is your household connected to electricity grid?

No

Yes

How much did the household spent monthly on buying electricity power on the most recent bill? (FCFA°)

How much did the household head spent on buying on air time in the past 30 days? (FCFA°)

How much did all household members together spend on buying air time in the past 30 days? (FCFA°)

HOUSEHOLD ASSETS / WEALTH INDICATORS

House

Does the household has House ?

No

Yes

Number of House owned

Total Current value of the House (in FCFA)

Solar Panel

Does the household has Solar Panel?

No

Yes

Number of Solar Panel owned

Total Current value of the Solar Panel (in FCFA)

Electricity Generator

Does the household has Electricity Generator?

No

Yes

Number of Electricity Generator owned

Total Current value of the Electricity Generator (in FCFA)

Total monthly expenditures for the operation and maintenance of the Electric Generator (FCFA)

Radio

Does the household has Radio?

- No
- Yes

Number of Radio owned

Total Current value of the Radio (in FCFA)

Television

Does the household has Television?

- No
- Yes

Number of Television owned

Total Current value of the Television (in FCFA)

Refrigerator

Does the household has Refrigerator?

- No
- Yes

Number of Refrigerator owned

Total Current value of the Refrigerator (in FCFA)

Mobile phone

Does the household has Mobile phone?

- No
- Yes

Number of Mobile phone owned

Total Current value of the Mobile phone (in FCFA)

Car

Does the household has Car?

No

Yes

Number of Car owned

Total Current value of the Car (in FCFA)

Motorcycle

Does the household has Motorcycle?

No

Yes

Number of Motorcycle owned

Total Current value of the Motorcycle (in FCFA)

Bicycle

Does the household has Bicycle?

No

Yes

Number of Bicycle owned

Total Current value of the Bicycle (in FCFA)

Cooking stoves*Does the household has Cooking stoves?* No Yes**Number of Cooking stoves owned**

Total Current value of the Cooking stoves (in FCFA)

Gas cylinder*Does the household has Gas cylinder?* No Yes**Number of Gas cylinder owned**

Total Current value of the Gas cylinder (in FCFA)

Kitchenware*Does the household has Kitchenware (pots, dishes, bowls, plastics)?* No Yes**Number of Kitchenware owned**

Total Current value of the Kitchenware (in FCFA)

Tractor

Does the household has Tractor

No

Yes

Number of Tractor owned

Total Current value of the Tractor (in FCFA)

Plough for tractor

Does the household has Plough for tractor?

No

Yes

Number of Plough for tractor owned

Total Current value of the Plough for tractor (in FCFA)

OX Plough

Does the household has OX Plough

No

Yes

Number of OX Plough owned

Total Current value of the OX Plough (in FCFA)

Oxcart

Does the household has Oxcart?

No

Yes

Number of Oxcart owned

Total Current value of the Oxcart (in FCFA)

Ox- weeder*Does the household has Ox- weeder?* No Yes**Number of Ox- weeder owned**

Total Current value of the Ox- weeder (in FCFA)

Hand Hoe*Does the household has Hand Hoe?* No Yes**Number of Hand Hoe owned**

Total Current value of the Hand Hoe (in FCFA)

Machete*Does the household has Machete?* No Yes**Number of Machete owned**

Total Current value of the Machete (in FCFA)

Sprayer for pesticides

Does the household has Sprayer for pesticides?

No

Yes

Number of Sprayer for pesticides owned

Total Current value of the Sprayer for pesticides (in FCFA)

Have Other Asset 1

Does the household has Other Asset?

No

Yes

» First other asset

Name of other asset 1

Number of Others Asset owned

Total Current value of the Other Asset 1 (in FCFA)

Have Other Asset 2

Does the household has Other Asset?

No

Yes

» Second other asset

Name of other asset 2

Number of Other Asset 2

Total Current value of the Other Asset 2 (in FCFA)

Have Other Asset 3*Does the household has Other Asset?* No Yes**» Third other asset****Name of other asset 3**

Number of Other Asset 3

Total Current value of the Other Asset 3 (in FCFA)

Have Other Asset 4*Does the household has Other Asset?* No Yes**» Fourth other asset****Name of other asset 4**

Number of Other Asset 4

Total Current value of the Other Asset 4 (in FCFA)

LIVESTOCK

Cattle

Do you have cattle?

- No
- Yes

How many cattle do you own?

Total Current value for your cattle

How many of these cattle are oxen trained for farming and transporting activities?

Donkeys and mules

Do you have donkeys and mules?

- No
- Yes

How many donkeys and mules do you own?

Total Current value for your donkeys and mules

How many of these donkeys and mules are trained for farming and transporting activities?

Goats

Do you have goats?

- No
- Yes

How many goats do you own?

Total Current value for your goats

Sheep

Do you have sheep?

No

Yes

How many sheep do you own?

Total Current value for your sheep

Poultry

Do you have poultry?

No

Yes

How many poultry do you own?

Total Current value for your poultry

Other animals

Do you have other animals?

No

Yes

Names of other animals owned

How many of other animals do you own?

Total Current value for your other animals

HEALTH FACILITIES

What is the distance from your house to the nearest health facility (clinic/hospital/dispensary)? (km)

Did you or any other household member attend a health facility (clinic/hospital/dispensary) for treatment in the past 12 months?

No

Yes

What was the total expenditure of all household members together at health facilities in the past 12 months? (FCFA)

What was the total expenditure of all household members together on medical treatments at other places (FCFA)

Did you or any other household member receive traditional medical treatment in the past the past 12 months?

No

Yes

What was the total expenditure of all household members together on traditional medical treatments in the past 12 months? (FCFA)

How many household members got poisoned with pesticides or bio-pesticides in your households in the past 12 months?

What was the household total expenditure on medical treatment of poisoning with pesticides or bio-pesticides in the past 12 months? (FCFA)

How many hired labourers who work on the household's farms got poisoned with pesticides or bio-pesticides in the past 12 months?

What was the hired labourers' total expenditure on medical treatment of poisoning with pesticides or bio-pesticides in the past 12 months? (FCFA)

how much of hired labourers' expenditures on medical treatment of poisoning with pesticides or bio-pesticides in the past 12 months were paid by the household?

10 stones = all monetary expenditures: how many 'stones' from the contribution?

DRINKING WATER

What is the main source of drinking water for your household?

- Piped water into dwelling
- Piped water to yard/plot
- Public tap/standpipe
- Protected permanent dug well
- Unprotected permanent dug well
- protected temporary dug well
- Unprotected temporary dug well
- Rainwater collection
- Cart with small tank/drum
- Surface water (river, dam, lake, pond, stream, canal, irrigation channels)
- Other (specify)

Please describe the main source of drinking water for your household

Note: Write NA if other modality expect other is selected

How long does it take to go there collect water and come back? (in minutes)

Do you treat your water in any way to make it safer to drink?

- No
- Yes

What do you usually do to the water to make it safer to drink?

- Boil
- Add bleach/chlorine
- Strain it through a cloth
- Use a water filter (ceramic, sand, composite, etc.)
- Solar disinfection
- Let it stand and settle
- Other (specify)

Please describe what you usually do to the water to make it safer to drink

SANITATION FACILITIES**What kind of toilet facility do the members of your household usually use?**

- Flush/pour flush to
- Ventilated improved pit latrine (VIP)
- Pit latrine with slab
- Pit latrine without slab/open pit
- Composting toilet
- Bucket
- Hanging toilet/hanging latrine
- No facilities or bush or field
- Other (specify)

Precision on "Flush/pour flush to" system

- piped sewer system
- septic tank
- pit latrine
- elsewhere

Please describe what kind of toilet facility the members of your household usually use.

Do you share this facility with other households?

- No
- Yes

How many minutes does it usually take you to get there for toilet purpose?

GPS Cordinates

Make sure the sky is clear (i.e, dot not stay under a tree or under shelter)

latitude (x.y °)

longitude (x.y °)

altitude (m)

précision (m)

Questionnaire completed on DATE

The date you finished the questionnaire

yyyy-mm-dd

Questionnaire completed on TIME

Indicate the hour you finished the questionnaire

hh:mm

Supervisor